

Impact of Formative Assessment on Learning, Motivation, and Stress Among MBBS Students: A Cross-Sectional Study in Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & Research Foundation, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh

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Abstract

Background: Formative assessment (FA) is an essential component of Competency-Based Medical Education (CBME), facilitating continuous learning and skill development in medical students. This study aim to analyse the impact of FA on academic performance, motivation, confidence, and student perceptions in an MBBS curriculum.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among MBBS students at Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & RF, Andhra Pradesh, using a structured questionnaire. A total of 132 Phase-I MBBS students who had completed at least three FA attempts participated. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Software version 20, employing descriptive and inferential statistics, including the Chi-square test.

Results: Among the 132 participants, 77.3% believed that FA was beneficial for their learning process, with 48.5% agreeing and 12.1% strongly agreeing that FA improved their academic performance. However, FA was associated with stress, as 91.7% of students reported experiencing some level of stress, with 35.6% feeling highly stressed. Despite FA's perceived benefits, 63.6% of students did not want an increase in its use in teaching. FA feedback motivated 39.4% of students to study harder, while 42.4% reported increased confidence in learning. However, 26.5% felt FA feedback decreased their confidence.

Academic dishonesty was reported among 21.2% of students, with a significant increase in later academic years ($p = 0.000$). A statistically significant association was observed between MBBS year and perceptions of FA benefits ($p = 0.008$), with first-year students showing the highest level of agreement.

Conclusion: While FA is widely acknowledged as a beneficial learning tool in medical education, its association with stress and mixed effects on motivation and confidence highlight areas for improvement. Students in later years exhibited increased academic pressure, leading to more instances of academic dishonesty and negative perceptions of FA. To enhance its effectiveness, a balanced approach is required, incorporating FA strategies that minimize stress while maintaining its role in academic improvement and self-regulated learning.

Keywords: Formative assessment, competency-based medical education, self-regulated learning, academic performance, stress.

INTRODUCTION

Formative assessment is a key component of Competency-Based Medical Education (CBME) and plays an essential role in helping medical students develop the skills required for professional practice. Within the MBBS curriculum, it supports ongoing learning by offering regular feedback, enabling students to track their progress and make improvements as needed. Unlike summative assessments, which focus on final outcomes, formative evaluations provide a low-pressure setting where students can evaluate their understanding without the stress of critical examinations. This approach allows them to pinpoint areas of weakness and address them effectively, helping to alleviate anxiety associated with exams¹.

The National Medical Commission (NMC) underscores the importance of formative assessment in medical education, promoting continuous feedback and personal growth. These assessments are woven into internal evaluation systems, blending formative and summative methods to optimize learning outcomes. The NMC guidelines advocate for a comprehensive evaluation framework that covers multiple dimensions, including cognitive abilities, practical skills, communication, and emotional competencies—areas often

overlooked in traditional testing methods. Additionally, the active involvement of faculty, such as Senior Residents and senior educators, is encouraged to strengthen the assessment process².

Self-regulated learning (SRL) is increasingly valued as a vital skill for lifelong learning in healthcare. Contemporary teaching strategies aim to nurture SRL in medical students through creative approaches like flipped classrooms and team-based learning. These methods encourage independent thought, active engagement, and critical reasoning, preparing students to stay abreast of medical advancements and tackle evolving clinical challenges throughout their professional lives³.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **STUDY DESIGN:** A cross-sectional study was conducted.
- **STUDY PARTICIPANTS:** The participants were students from Phase-I, Phase-II, and Phase-III MBBS.
- **STUDY SETTING** The study was carried out at Konaseema Institute of Medical Sciences & RF, Amalapuram, Andhra Pradesh.
- **SAMPLE TECHNIQUES:** Convenient sampling
- **INCLUSION CRITERIA:** Phase-1 MBBS students who had attempted a minimum of three formative assessments during their first year of MBBS were included in the study.
- **EXCLUSION CRITERIA:**
 1. Students who were unwilling to participate in the study were excluded.
 2. Students who had attempted fewer than three formative assessments were also excluded.
- **ETHICAL CONSIDERATION:** Institutional ethics committee approval was taken and informed consent was obtained.
- **DATA COLLECTION:** Data collection was done using pre tested & pre structured questionnaire. Google forms were sent to all students and asked to be filled.
- **DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:-** Data was entered using a Microsoft Excel 2016 spreadsheet. Summarization and analysis of data were carried out by using IBM

SPSS Software version 20 (licensed). Descriptive Statistics: Frequency, Percentage.

Inferential Statistics: Chi-square test.

Results

Figure:1

Table:1 The Impact of Formative Assessment on Academic Performance in study participants

Do you think FA is beneficial for your learning process?		
Yes	102	77.3
No	30	22.7
Have you noticed an improvement in your grades due to FA?		
Yes		
No		
Do you think FA helps improve your academic performance?		
Strongly agree	16	12.1
Agree	64	48.5
Neutral	30	22.7
Disagree	12	9.1
Strongly Disagree	10	7.6

Do you feel stressed when giving FA?		
Vary very much	47	35.6
Sometimes	74	56.1
Not at all	11	8.3
Would you like teachers to use more FA in their teachings?		
Yes	48	36.4
No	84	63.6

The majority 102(77.3%) believe that FA benefits their learning process. Additionally, many students agree that FA helps improve their academic performance, with 48.5% agreeing and 12.1% strongly agreeing. However, a portion of students remains neutral (22.7%) or disagrees (16.7%), indicating varying perspectives on its effectiveness. However, when it comes to stress levels, a significant number of students (91.7%) experience some level of stress while giving FA, with 35.6% feeling stressed "very much." Interestingly, despite the perceived benefits, a larger percentage 84(63.6%) do not want teachers to use more FA in their teachings.

Table:2 The Impact of Formative Assessment Feedback on Motivation and Confidence

Does receiving FA feedback motivate you to study harder?		
Yes	52	39.4
No	35	26.5
Sometimes	45	34.1
How does FA impact your confidence in learning?		
It increases my confidence	56	42.4
No effect	41	31.1
It decreases my confidence	35	26.5

The majority of students 52(39.4%) feel motivated to study harder upon receiving FA feedback, while 34.1% report that it sometimes has this effect. However, a

smaller percentage 35(26.5%) do not find it motivating. In terms of confidence, FA feedback has a positive effect on many students, with 42.4% stating that it increases their confidence. However, for 31.1%, FA feedback has no effect, and for 26.5%, it actually decreases their confidence.

Table: 3 showing Study and Preparation Habits for Formative Assessment

Have you ever bunk other classes to prepare for FA?		
Yes	84	63.6
No	48	36.4
Did you bunk the FA?		
Yes	38	28.8
No	94	71.2
Did you ever copied in FA?		
Yes	28	21.2
No	104	78.8
Do you prefer night out all night to prepare for FA?		
Yes	47	35.6
Sometimes	27	20.5
No	58	43.9

Many students 84(63.6%) admitted to skipping other classes to prepare for their FA, However, when it came to bunk the FA itself, a majority (71.2%) chose to attend rather than avoid the exam. And 78.8% of students stated they never engaged in copying during the FA, showing a commitment to honest performance. However, 21.2% admitted to resorting to unfair means, reflecting the pressures some students face.

Table:4 showing, Association between Perception and Practices Related to Formative Assessment among MBBS Students

	Phase in MBBS			Total	Chi-square	P-Value
	1st year	2nd year	3rd year			
Do you think FA is beneficial for your learning process?						
Yes	41	29	32	102	9.580	0.008
No	10	17	3	30		
Would you like teachers to use more FA in their teachings?						
Yes	13	18	17	48	5.012	0.082
No	38	28	18	84		
Have you ever bunk other classes to prepare for FA?						
Yes	23	40	21	84	18.585	0.000
No	28	6	14	48		
Did you bunk the FA?						
Yes	19	8	11	38	4.817	0.90
No	32	38	24	94		
Did you ever copied in FA?						
Yes	2	12	14	28	17.170	0.000
No	49	34	21	104		
Do you think FA helps improve your academic performance?						
Strongly agree	6	5	5	16	7.215	0.514
Agree	25	18	21	64		
Neutral	10	13	7	30		

Disagree	5	5	2	12		
Strongly Disagree	5	5	0	10		

A majority of students found FA beneficial, with the highest agreement in the 1st year, though the 2nd-year students showed more uncertainty ($p = 0.008$). Preference for increased FA use was slightly higher in the 3rd year but was not statistically significant ($p = 0.082$). A significant number of 2nd-year students (40) reported skipping other classes to prepare for FA, indicating higher academic pressure at this stage ($p = 0.000$). Academic dishonesty was reported more in later years, with a sharp rise in copying cases among 2nd- and 3rd-year students compared to the 1st year ($p = 0.000$). Regarding FA's impact on academic performance, most students either agreed or remained neutral, with minimal disagreement across all years, though the association was not significant ($p = 0.514$).

DISCUSSIONS

In the present study, a significant proportion of students recognized the benefits of formative assessment (FA) in their learning process. Out of 132 participants, 102 students (77.3%) perceived FA as beneficial, with 48.5% agreeing and 12.1% strongly agreeing that FA contributes to academic improvement. These findings align with the study by Arja SB et al.,⁴ where 83% of students found FA helpful in achieving learning objectives, and 81% believed it enhanced their knowledge. Similarly, research by Hill DA et al. reported that 89% of respondents supported the integration of FA into the teaching process.⁵ Collectively, these findings reinforce the widespread acknowledgment of FA as an effective learning tool that aids both academic performance and comprehension.

Although the majority of students in our study viewed FA favourably, its direct impact on academic grades was not explicitly assessed. However, the study by Arja SB et al. demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in GPA following FA implementation, with an increase from 2.29 to 2.83 ($p < 0.001$) and 74% of students experiencing academic progress.⁴ Furthermore, Das S et al.⁵ reported that 80.8% of students felt FA encouraged deeper learning and regular study habits. These findings complement our study's results, where many students acknowledged the role of FA in enhancing academic performance.

Despite its perceived advantages, FA was also associated with stress among students. Our study found that 91.7% of students experienced some level of stress during FA, with 35.6% reporting high levels of stress. This aligns with the findings of Das S et al.,⁶ who reported that 36.4% of students felt that frequent FA hindered independent learning and negatively impacted performance in summative exams. These results suggest that while FA is beneficial, excessive implementation may contribute to academic pressure and anxiety among students.

The impact of FA feedback on student motivation and confidence produced mixed results. In our study, 39.4% of students felt motivated to study harder upon receiving FA feedback, whereas 34.1% reported occasional motivation, and 26.5% found it unhelpful in fostering motivation. Additionally, 42.4% of students reported increased confidence following FA feedback, while 31.1% experienced no effect, and 26.5% reported a decline in confidence. In contrast, Das S et al. found that 78% of respondents valued FA feedback in bridging learning gaps, and 76.8% believed it helped faculty identify students' weaknesses. These differences suggest that while FA benefits many students, it may also highlight academic shortcomings, potentially leading to diminished confidence in some cases.⁶

Our study identified a statistically significant association between MBBS year and students' perceptions of FA ($p = 0.008$). First-year students exhibited the highest level of agreement regarding FA's benefits, whereas second-year students demonstrated more uncertainty, possibly due to increased academic workload. While third-year students showed a slightly higher preference for FA, the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.082$). These findings indicate that as students advance through medical school, their perspectives on FA may evolve in response to changing academic demands and expectations.

The positive impact of FA observed in our study is consistent with previous research. For instance, Lakhtakia R et al.⁷ highlighted both immediate and long-term benefits of FA, including increased motivation, skill acquisition, and critical thinking. These findings align with our study, where many students acknowledged FA's role in fostering motivation and academic growth. However, concerns regarding stress and reluctance toward increased FA usage highlight the need for refining FA implementation strategies to minimize anxiety while preserving its educational advantages.

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8. The study done by Arja SB et al, showed that, 58 out of 67 students, showed a significant improvement in GPA after implementing formative assessment, increasing from **2.29 (SD±0.76575)** to **2.83 (SD±0.624745)** ($t(58) = 0.000567, p < .001$), with **74%** experiencing improvement, **14%** a decline, and **12%** showing no change. **98.3%** of students were aware of formative assessment, **83%** found it helpful in achieving learning objectives, **81%** believed it enhanced knowledge, and **65.5%** saw it as a strong predictor of self-evaluation. On a **1-10 scale**, students rated the **effectiveness of formative assessment at 6.9 (SD±2.46)**, **improvement at 6.8 (SD±2.44)**, **timeliness of feedback at 6.5 (SD±2.80)**, and **satisfaction with faculty feedback at 6.6 (SD±2.82)**. Additionally, **62.7%** of students were satisfied with faculty feedback, confirming the overall positive impact of formative assessment on learning outcomes

In Hill DA et al, Eighty-nine per cent of respondents felt that formative assessment should be incorporated into the teaching process.

The students' overall score of agreement with the AaL educational intervention was 84%, which was strongly correlated with scores for ease and impact on a 5-point Likert-type scale. The themes that emerged from the qualitative analysis included prominent characteristics, immediate gains, and expected long-term benefits of engagement. The prominent characteristics included individuals' engagement, effective interdependencies, novelty, and time requirements. The identified immediate gains highlighted increased motivation and acquisition of knowledge and skills. The expected long-term benefits included critical thinking, problem solving, and clinical reasoning showed in Lakhtakia R et al study.

In Das S et al, study showed that, Majority of the respondents (78%) favored that the feedback collected from formative assessment remains important for them as it helps to fill their learning gaps. Respondents by large (76.8%) also agreed that formative assessment helps the faculty to identify student's weak point. A huge percentage (80.8%) of respondents was in agreement that formative assessment inspires them for deep learning and regular study. However, a fair number of respondents (36.4%) thought that frequently scheduled formative assessment impede their independent learning thus negatively impact their performance in summative exam.

- Faculty development activities are crucial for the successful implementation of formative assessments, especially in the low resource setting.

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Effective and timely feedback is the key to the formative assessments.

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Feedback needs to be focused on that particular performance rather than generalized or vague.

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Feedback needs to be centered around on how to improve the performance in the future and learning behaviors rather than criticism.

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Joint action plan by the instructor and the learner is essential for effective formative assessment implementation.